

Design & Analysis of Circular ESR With Varied Zones

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Abstract— Water tanks are extremely crucial for public utility and for industrial structure as they serve vital storage facility for water supply. As we know elevated water tanks were heavily damaged or collapsed during earthquake. The occurrence of potential errors in the tank staging system might have resulted from a lack of knowledge concerning proper support behaviour against seismic effects and also due to the inappropriate selection of geometric staging patterns. The study describes, design and analysis of supporting system of circular elevated water tanks having same capacity for different seismic zone (II and IV) . Shear force, Seismic Axial force, and seismic bending moment are calculated under each column by Staad Pro Connect.

Keywords— Circular Elevated Water Tanks, Seismic Axial Force, Seismic Bending Moment, Shear Force

I. INTRODUCTION

In India, the reinforced concrete structures are designed and built to provide various needs. Reinforced concrete overhead water tanks are largely utilized to supply the safe drinking water. Most water supply systems in developing countries like India, where urbanizing is increasing day by day, rely heavily on overhead storage tanks, resulting in the necessary construction of a greater number of water tanks. Storage reservoirs and overhead tanks are employed to store water, liquid petroleum, petroleum products, and other similar liquids. The common materials used for the development of tanks include concrete, steel, and masonry. RCC is commonly utilized in construction because it is supposed to be a durable material giving long maintenance-free service. Make sure to consider the important aspects of designing and constructing reinforced concrete structures, despite the challenges of improper materials or inadequate maintenance practices.

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Objectives

- To make a study going through the design of water tanks
- Design of circular overhead water tank by limit state method.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. A.D.V.S. Uma Maheswari, et al As we know from the past, several reinforced concrete elevated water tanks were severely loss or collapsed during earthquakes all around the world. As a result of general findings, the collapse of the raised tank's supporting system is more critical than the other structural sections of the tank.
2. M. Sai Ramya, et al System's lifeline is its elevated water tanks, which are its important structures. As a result of earthquakes, elevated water tanks have been collapsed in the past. Lack of suitable support systems for the water tank and incorrect staging are responsible for the loss.
3. Nanjunda, et al A contribution to the water tank was subjected to dynamic forces in the present study, which focused on its reactivity. Large water masses at the top of a fine staging are the leading factor in determining whether an overhead water tank will fail after an earthquake.
4. Nitesh Singh, et al Water tanks are designed to withstand dead load + live load, wind load, and seismic loads, according to IS rules of procedure. Tanks are often planned for wind forces and not even examined for earthquake loads, believing that they will be safe under seismic forces after they are designed for wind forces. However, this is not always the case. A water tank with an H-shaped inlet is studied for Indian circumstances. Due to the fact that wind flows relative to the face of the earth and exerts loads on structures standing on the ground, the wind's effect on elevated structures is quite important.
5. Prashant Bansode Structures such as reinforced concrete elevated water tanks are extremely valuable. During and after earthquakes, they are regarded to be essential life belt. Like an inverted pendulum, an elevated water tank is composed of a huge water mass perched on the topmost stage in its design.
6. Rupachandra, et al 6 In industries, liquid storage facilities are used to hold chemicals, oil products, and water for public water distribution networks, among other things. The behavior of cylindrical liquid storage tanks under seismic stresses has been determined according to the IS 1893:2002 draft code part II. Software (STAAD-PRO) based on finite

element modeling (FEM) that determine earthquake-induced forces on tank systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

IV. DESIGNING OF CIRCULAR WATER TANK IN STAAD PRO

Fig 1. The Model Of Structure With All The Beam And Nodes

Fig 2. Assigning Concrete Material To Structure

Fig 3. The Model with Fixed Support

IV. STAAD PRO RESULT STAAD PRO

Query Concrete Design Beam no. 30
Design Code: IS-456

IS-456 BEAM NO.	LIMIT 30	STATE DESIGN	DESIGN RESULTS
M30	Fe415 (Main)	Fe415 (Sec.)	
LENGTH: 3444.2 mm	SIZE: 300.0 mm X 300.0 mm	COVER: 30.0 mm	

SUMMARY OF REINF. AREA (Sq.mm)					
SECTION	0.0 mm	861.0 mm	1722.1 mm	2583.1 mm	3444.2 mm
TOP REINF.	162.83 (Sq. mm)				
BOTTOM REINF.	162.83 (Sq. mm)				

SUMMARY OF PROVIDED REINF. AREA					
SECTION	0.0 mm	861.0 mm	1722.1 mm	2583.1 mm	3444.2 mm
TOP REINF.	3-10d 1 layer(s)				
BOTTOM REINF.	3-10d 1 layer(s)				
SHEAR REINF.	2 legged 8d @ 120 mm c/c				

STAAD Pro Query Concrete Design Beam no. 54
Design Code: IS-456

IS-456 COLUMN NO.	LIMIT 54	STATE DESIGN	DESIGN RESULTS
M30	Fe415 (Main)	Fe415 (Sec.)	
LENGTH: 4000.0 mm	CROSS SECTION: 300.0 mm dia.	COVER: 40.0 mm	

** GUIDING LOAD CASE: 2 BRACED LONG COLUMN

REQD. STEEL AREA : 834.78 Sq.mm.
REQD. CONCRETE AREA: 69851.06 Sq.mm.
MAIN REINFORCEMENT : Provide 8 - 12 dia. (1.28%, 904.78 Sq.mm.)
(Equally distributed)
TIE REINFORCEMENT : Provide 8 mm dia. circular ties @ 190 mm c/c

SECTION CAPACITY BASED ON REINFORCEMENT REQUIRED (KNS-MET)

Puz : 1202.81 Muz1 : 30.96 Muy1 : 30.96

INTERACTION RATIO: 1.00 (as per Cl. 39.6, IS456:2000)

SECTION CAPACITY BASED ON REINFORCEMENT PROVIDED (KNS-MET)

WORST LOAD CASE: 2
Puz : 1223.66 Muz : 32.81 Muy : 32.81 IR: 0.94
STAAD SPACE

-- PAGE NO. 90

STAAD.Pro Query Concrete Design
Beam no. 22
Design Code: IS-456

IS-456 LIMIT STATE DESIGN
BEAM NO. 22 DESIGN RESULTS

M30 Fe415 (Main) Fe415 (Sec.)
LENGTH: 3444.2 mm SIZE: 300.0 mm X 300.0 mm COVER: 30.0 mm

SUMMARY OF REINF. AREA (Sq.mm)

SECTION	0.0 mm	861.0 mm	1722.1 mm	2583.1 mm	3444.2 mm
TOP REINF.	162.22 (Sq. mm)	162.83 (Sq. mm)	162.83 (Sq. mm)	272.05 (Sq. mm)	539.84 (Sq. mm)
BOTTOM REINF.	616.36 (Sq. mm)	333.33 (Sq. mm)	162.83 (Sq. mm)	162.83 (Sq. mm)	162.83 (Sq. mm)

SUMMARY OF PROVIDED REINF. AREA

SECTION	0.0 mm	861.0 mm	1722.1 mm	2583.1 mm	3444.2 mm
TOP REINF.	3-10d 1 layer(s)	3-10d 1 layer(s)	3-10d 1 layer(s)	4-10d 1 layer(s)	7-10d 1 layer(s)
BOTTOM REINF.	8-10d 2 layer(s)	5-10d 1 layer(s)	3-10d 1 layer(s)	3-10d 1 layer(s)	3-10d 1 layer(s)
SHEAR REINF.	2 legged 8d @ 120 mm c/c				

IS-456 LIMIT STATE DESIGN
COLUMN NO. 55 DESIGN RESULTS

M30 Fe415 (Main) Fe415 (Sec.)
LENGTH: 4000.0 mm CROSS SECTION: 300.0 mm dia. COVER: 40.0 mm

** GUIDING LOAD CASE: 1 BRACED LONG COLUMN

REQD. STEEL AREA : 1070.16 Sq.mm.
REQD. CONCRETE AREA: 69615.67 Sq.mm.
MAIN REINFORCEMENT : Provide 10 - 12 dia. (1.60%, 1130.97 Sq.mm.)
(Equally distributed)
TIE REINFORCEMENT : Provide 8 mm dia. circular ties @ 190 mm c/c

SECTION CAPACITY BASED ON REINFORCEMENT REQUIRED (KNS-MET)

Puz : 1272.90 Muz1 : 36.40 Muy1 : 36.40

INTERACTION RATIO: 1.00 (as per Cl. 39.6, IS456:2000)

SECTION CAPACITY BASED ON REINFORCEMENT PROVIDED (KNS-MET)

WORST LOAD CASE: 1
Puz : 1291.01 Muz : 37.50 Muy : 37.82 IR: 0.97

STAAD Pro Query Concrete Design
Beam no. 55
Design Code:IS-456

CONCLUSION

This Circular Overhead Tank was designed for a capacity of about 200 m³; it has been designed by using M30 grade of concrete and HYSD bar of grade Fe415. The design results obtained after successful completion were error free and safe. The design results were matched with manual calculations which showed the small difference amount of reinforcement. We concluded the safe design of this Overhead Water Tank after obtaining Error free design results from Staad Pro.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.D.V.S. Uma Maheswari, B. Sravani Performance of elevated circular water tank in different seismic zones International Journal for Technological Research in Engineering ISSN: 2347 - 4718 Volume 3, Issue 5, January-2016
- [2] Ankita Singh, Prashant "Khutemate seismic analysis of the water tank for variation in bracings patterns and water fill conditions", ISSN-2349-5162, Volume 8, Issue:1,2021 JETIR January 2021.
- [3] Jain, S.K., and Sajjad, S.U. (1993). "A Review of need in Indian codes for a seismic design of ESR".
- [4] M. V. Gaikwad, M. N. Mangulkar, "Seismic Performance of Circular Elevated Water Tank with Framed Staging Structure" International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET) Volume 4, Issue 4, May - June 2013, pp. 159167, 2013.
- [5] Nitesh J Singh1, Mohammad Ishtiaque "Design analysis & comparison of H- intake type water tank for different wind speed and seismic zones as per Indian code", International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology ISSN: 2319-1163 ISSN: 2321-7308 Volume: 04 Issue: 09 | September-2015.
- [6] O. R. Jaiswal and S. K. Jain, "Modified Proposed Provisions for a seismic Design of Liquid Storage Tanks: Part II -Commentary and Examples", Journal of Structural Engineering Volume. 32, No.4, 2005.

- [7] IS456:2000, "Code of Practice for Plain and Reinforced Concrete", I.S.I., New Delhi
- [8] IS 3370-1 (2009) is a code of practice for concrete structures that store liquids
- [9] IS 875 (part 1) - 1987: Indian Standard Codes provides design dead loads for buildings and structures.
- [10] IS 875 (part 3) - 1987: Indian Standard Codes provides design wind loads for buildings and structures.